

Microplastics concentration from Primary Sludge Liquor using UF membranes

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Abstract

This study is focused on the supernatant stream of primary sludge thickening, named Primary Sludge Liquor (PSL), from wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Microplastics (MPs) separation trials were conducted by ultrafiltration membrane technique (UF) to determine its optimal functioning conditions. The objective was to concentrate microplastics (MPs) in the reject stream while maintaining nutrients of interest in the permeate stream. Results have shown that UH050 membrane achieves its best performance at low transmembrane pressure, such as 0.5 bar. Permeate flux remained stable after the initial decay. Volume reduction factor (VRF) of 2 was achieved leading to MPs concentration in the rejection stream. The results suggest promising pathways for enhancing nutrient recovery and MPs concentration, paving the way for more sustainable waste management practices. Ongoing experiments are being tested in order to broaden these studies to MF techniques and other streams such as centrate from sludge dewatering process, coming after an anaerobic digester.

Keywords

Microplastics; Primary Sludge Liquor; Ultrafiltration; Nutrients

INTRODUCTION

MPs have emerged as a significant environmental concern due to their persistence and potential adverse effects on aquatic ecosystems. WWTPs play a crucial role in mitigating the release of MPs into the environment. However, conventional treatment processes often fall short in completely removing these contaminants, leading to their accumulation in both effluent and sludge.

This study focuses on the Primary Sludge Liquor (PSL) and the application of UF technique to enhance the separation and concentration of MPs. Ultrafiltration is a pressure-driven membrane process that effectively removes particulate matter, including MPs, in the reject stream while allowing dissolved nutrients to pass through into the permeate to achieve nutrients recovery. This approach not only addresses the issue of MPs pollution but also promotes the recovery of essential nutrients, contributing to more sustainable wastewater management practices. In fact, the authors intend to take a step forward from previous studies such as Cifuentes-Cabezas et al., (2024). These authors optimized nutrients recovery from anaerobically digested sludge centrate, while Navajas-Valiente et al. (2024) considered membranes technologies for nutrients recovery and MPs concentration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample pretreatment

PSL samples were characterized before and after the pretreatment and the UF process. As a pretreatment step, the samples were filtered to partially remove the suspended solids, thereby protecting the ultrafiltration membranes used in subsequent tests. The filtration was conducted using a 100-micron sieve, allowing for the observation of MPs retained on either side of the filtration process.

Ultrafiltration tests

Ultrafiltration at constant concentration

Ultrafiltration experiments were conducted using a laboratory-scale membrane plant. The feed stream was pumped from an 8-liter capacity feed tank to a Rayflow membrane module (Orelis, France), which housed a flat sheet membrane with a total active surface area of 0.0129 m². Permeate flux was measured with a precision balance (0.01 g) (Kern, Germany), and the data were recorded using a data acquisition system. The feed tank was equipped with a refrigeration system to maintain the temperature at 25°C. The experimental setup can be seen in Figure 1. The authors chose a UH050 P, Mycrodin Nadir (Germany) PES flat-sheet membrane which had a 50kDa MWCO.

Figure 1. Ultrafiltration experimental setup

The membrane was initially compacted, and its permeability (K) was determined. Besides, a test was conducted in constant concentration mode, where both the concentrate and permeate streams were recirculated back to the feed tank. This setup allowed the study of the influence of transmembrane pressure (TMP) on each membrane's performance. The ultrafiltration tests were performed under total recirculation mode with a fixed cross-flow velocity (CFV) of 1.5 m·s⁻¹, while varying the TMP between 0.5 and 2 bar.

Ultrafiltration at variable concentration

The membrane was evaluated in variable concentration mode, where only the concentrate stream was recirculated, under the selected TMP. This setup was used to observe the separation behaviour of both nutrients and MPs. The tests were conducted with a fixed CFV of 1.5 m·s⁻¹ and a TMP of 0.5 bar, which was identified as the optimal TMP condition during the constant concentration tests.

Membrane cleaning

After each test, the membrane was cleaned to restore their initial permeability. Optimal cleaning criterion relied on achieving at least 90% of the initial permeability. The cleaning procedure consisted in a chemical cleaning with 1% (v/v) P3-Ultrasil 110 (Ecolab, Spain) at 45°C, followed by 10-minute rinse with osmotized water to remove any chemical residues from the membrane and the laboratory setup.

Analytical characterizations

The feed, concentrate and permeate streams from each test were analysed. pH and conductivity were measured using a GLP 21+ pH meter and a GLP 31+ EC meter (Crison, Spain), respectively. Turbidity was assessed with a TL 2310 turbidimeter (Hach, Spain). Total nitrogen (N_{total}), ammonium (N-NH₄⁺), total phosphorus (P_{total}), phosphate (P-PO₄³⁻) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) were measured using Merck kits, following the manufacturer's experimental protocols. Total solids (TS), volatile total solids (VTS) suspended solids (SS) and volatile suspended solids (VSS) were measured. All measurements were performed in duplicate.

Microparticles and Microplastics characterization

The pretreatment involved oxidizing the organic matter in the samples using hydrogen peroxide (30% w/w, LABBOX Spain) to prevent interference with MPs quantification. For this, 25 mL of each sample was mixed with 2.5 mL of hydrogen peroxide and heated at 60°C for 2 hours on a stirring hot plate. After oxidation, the samples were filtered through a glass microfiber filter and oven-dried at 60°C for 2 hours before microparticles (MPr) counting (Bretas Alvim et al., 2020).

The quantification of MPr in the samples was carried out through visual inspection using a stereomicroscope (LEICA S APO), as shown in Figure 2. To facilitate counting, a plastic structure was placed on the top of the filter dividing it in eight equal sections. Raman analysis was performed to identify MPs using the ALPHA300 M+ (Witec, Germany) as follows: a 633 nm red laser, a wavelength range of 0 to 3500 cm^{-1} , 20 ac, and an integration time of 0.5 seconds. TrueMatch Spectral Database (Witec) was used employing spectral libraries from Munno et al. (2020).

Figure 2. Stereomicroscope MPr counting

RESULTS

Ultrafiltration tests

The permeability of UH050 was determined to be $234.65 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{bar}^{-1}$. After measuring J_p (permeate flux) for the different TMP tested, no notorious improvement was shown by increasing this pressure due to gel layer formation, so variable concentration was carried out at 0.5 bar to reduce energy consumption and foiling.

Table 1 presents the characterization results of the samples following the described tests. It is evident that the pretreatment stage slightly reduces some values, since the only purpose was separating high-size suspended solids. COD and N are significantly concentrated in the UF reject stream. However, phosphorus shows only a slight concentration increase in this stream.

Table 1. PSL characterization previous and after filtration. Permeate and reject characterization at UF variable concentration mode (0.5 bar - VRF = 2).

		Initial	After filtration	UF-Permeate	UF-Concentrate
COD-total	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	2010	1744	796	2564
COD-soluble	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	1014	632	-	584
N_T -total	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	143	138	74	181
N_T -soluble	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	91	80	-	67
N-NH_4^+ -total	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	101.8	82.0	77.2	75.6
N-NH_4^+ -soluble	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	97.2	73.6	-	78.4
P_T -total	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	64.4	63.6	44	69.6
P_T -soluble	$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$	56.4	32.4	-	29.6

MPs characterization

Regarding the quantification of MPr, Figure 3 (a) shows that the feed stream to the membranes is relatively reduced (<200 MPr/L) compared to the total PSL before the 100-micron prefilter (>600 MPr/L). Figure 3 (b) highlights that after achieving a VRF of 2, the fragments are concentrated 1.63 times in a stream with half the initial volume. The presence of these fragments can be observed in all PSL streams, feed, reject and permeate. However, the amount of particulate material in the permeate stream was significantly reduced. 35.00% of the MPr in the PSL were identified, with 14.29% of these being natural fragments. Finally, Figure 3 (c) emphasizes the characterization of MPs, noting that many of these MPs are PE and PP, which are polymers lighter than water.

Figure 3. a) MPr concentration in PSL; b) MPr concentration after UF at variable concentration; c) MPs characterisation in PSL. PS (Polystyrene), PE (Polyethylene), PE-PP (copolymer Polyethylene-Polypropylene), PP (Polypropylene).

CONCLUSIONS

The experiments conducted have successfully established a methodology for of concentration of MPs with high efficiency. The results demonstrate the potential to concentrate MPs in a smaller volume, facilitating subsequent targeted treatments. This approach not only aids in the effective removal of MPs but also would allow for the further recovery of valuable nutrients from the UF permeate stream, which can be repurposed for beneficial uses. Ongoing experiments are focused on evaluating various membranes with different permeability and molecular weight cut-offs, as well as other relevant streams from the WWTP. These efforts aim to identify the optimal conditions for the proposed removal of MPs, enhancing the overall efficiency and sustainability of the treatment process.

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